

Pedagogical and Psychological Role of Moral Qualities in the Leaders of Preschool Education Organizations

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Abstract:

In this article, the pedagogical-psychological role of moral qualities in the leaders of preschool educational organizations, moral qualities, some moral qualities and their place in pedagogical activity, pedagogical awareness is explained in detail.

Keywords: pedagogical-psychological role of moral qualities in preschool educational organization leaders, moral qualities, some moral qualities and their place in pedagogical activities, pedagogical consciousness.

Establishing a legal democratic state, civil society in our country, further liberalization of all aspects of the life of our society increases the status of issues of professional skills and moral aspects of the spiritual image of the leading personnel. This is the reason why the leader of our country attaches great importance to the training, morale, and potential of the personnel, and calls for strengthening the public control over the activities of the leading personnel. Leaders move the society, awaken the creative forces existing in the people, revive the socio-economic life. Of course, for this, it is necessary for the leader to become an example in the minds of the public, to be able to convince people of his word, to be able to follow the people. "...today, a leader is not only the owner of a specific profession, but first of all, he must be worthy of the people's trust with his activity and humanity, possess high intellectual thinking, be far-sighted, always strive for innovation, and keep pace with the times. "He should be a persistent person" [1].

The great scholar of the Middle Ages, Abu Nasr Farabi, in his many works put forward scientific and philosophical ideas about the sanctity of knowledge, morality, loyalty, humanity, education, work and vocational training. For example: in his works "Risala fit tanbih al-saadat" (Treatise on the Ways to Happiness), "The City of Virtuous People" and other works, he describes in detail his dreams of a good, perfect, happy society [2].

He emphasizes that the pedagogical and didactic principles, forms and methods of the educational process, founded by Muhammad al-Khorazmi, are as follows [3]:

- describing and explaining the essence of the observed event and event;
- question-answer method;
- experience, method of observation;
- algorithmic method;
- independence;
- Creative activity.

Analyzing the problem of comprehensive human development, Abu Nasr Farabi [4] emphasizes that the role of the teacher in the educational process is particularly important. The doctrine based on the thinker expresses the following main ideas:

- organization of spiritual education and training of intellectual qualities in a person guarantees his maturity;
- decency is the most basic of the moral qualities manifested in the person being educated, and serves as a basis for educating noble qualities in a person. It is very important to explain to them that human behavior and manners are important spiritual and moral qualities with the help of life examples;
- the formation of will in a student depends in many ways on the environment and the content of educational activities [5].

According to Abu Nasr Farabi, it is appropriate to use the following methods in the process of organizing education: instilling theoretical concepts into the minds of students and educating them about ethnic qualities, persuasive methods, as well as influencing intuition and feelings based on an individual approach.

According to Alloma, a teacher should have the following qualities:

- sensory organs are perfectly developed; strong memory, observation; to be fond of the art of public speaking and mastering knowledge;
- to abstain from food and drink, to be indifferent to wealth.

Pedagogical, didactic principles, forms and methods of education highly appreciated by Abu Nasr Farabi:

- theoretical and practical direction of education;
- scientific and practical importance of knowledge;
- systematicity, logic and sequence;
- connection with life;
- be understandable;
- observation and experiments;

- methods of dialectical, evidential, argumentative, rhetorical and poetic reasoning;
- method of induction and deduction;
- performing and repeating exercises [6].

Abu Raikhan Beruni [7] is a supporter of democratic pedagogy by the essence of his views. He tried to thoroughly study consciousness, the process of perception and its passage. He scientifically substantiated the forms and methods of teaching that activate cognitive activity.

Beruniy states that the following pedagogical principles, forms and methods of education have an incomparable role in the development of a person:

- comprehensibility of the given information (when imparting general knowledge, clarifying the essence of unfamiliar (distant) objects based on familiar (nearby) objects to the student, substantiation of unknown concepts on the basis of known knowledge guarantees positive results. draws attention to the lashes;
- arming students with scientific foundations (in this process, to familiarize the student with scientific literature, to form the skills of carrying out experiments and practical observations in it, constantly repeating the acquired information (notes that going helps the thorough assimilation of knowledge).

What should be the spirituality of a leader? What ideas form its basis? These issues are reflected in each of the president's speeches. "...pleasing the people, not being far from the concerns of the population, living with their pain requires every leader to critically look at his work and ask himself the question whether I am meeting these requirements or not, "requires increasing responsibility, timely performance of assigned tasks and unconditional obedience to the law..." [8]

In this sense, the leader of our country is always paying attention to the further improvement of the activities of the leading personnel who can conduct public policy in all areas and sectors of the country and carry out leadership work in the interests of people.

The head of a preschool educational organization is not just a position, but a big responsibility. They are entrusted with the important task of not only organizing the activities of the educational institution, but also forming the moral and moral image of the young generation. Therefore, the moral qualities of leaders have an important place not only in their personal lives, but also in their pedagogical activities.

The moral qualities embodied in the leader, his behavior, manners, attitude towards others serve as a unique example for those around him, especially young children.

Some moral qualities that are important in the leaders of preschool education organizations and their role in pedagogical activities:

1. Fairness: The leader should be impartial and fair to every employee, child and parent, not to single out anyone, and not to be motivated by personal interests when making decisions. This creates a healthy atmosphere in the team, strengthens mutual trust and respect.
2. Honesty: A leader must keep his word, fulfill his promises, and not abuse trust. This quality has a positive effect on team members and encourages them to be honest.
3. Responsibility: The leader must fulfill the tasks entrusted to him seriously and feel responsible for every decision. It is important to effectively organize the activities of this organization and ensure that children receive quality education.
4. Compassion: The leader should be kind and caring towards children, parents, employees, understand and support their problems. This quality helps to create a warm and friendly

atmosphere in the preschool.

5. Humility: A leader should not flaunt his knowledge and position to others, respect the opinions of others, and not be afraid to admit his mistakes. This quality creates a basis for healthy communication and cooperation in the team.

The above-mentioned moral qualities play an important role in the success of the leaders of the preschool educational organization in their pedagogical activities, and in the development of children as mature individuals in all respects.

Pedagogical ethics is understood as the activity of a teacher in accordance with ethical standards and ethics, pedagogical professional code of ethics of communities. Pedagogical ethics of the teacher is based on the moral basis, with the help of which the values and relevant categories of pedagogical ethics are realized, which knowledge of the phenomena of reality [9].

Heads of organizations are recommended to lead pedagogues regardless of their position [10].

The moral qualities of leaders are very important in an educational institution. They affect not only the leader's personal reputation, but also the environment of the entire organization, and the relationship between employees and students.

Pedagogical justice is unique. It describes the objectivity of the teacher, the level of his moral development, his services and public recognition. Unconditional respect for the human dignity of each participant in the professional pedagogical duty is the pedagogical process, the confirmation of humanity, the implementation of the principle of respect for the personality of the student, and the unity of the demands on him [11].

Professional honor - determines normative requirements, implies a measure of respect for behavior and personality, which is deserved by all participants of pedagogy [12].

For the head of a preschool educational organization, moral qualities are important not only in personal life, but also in professional activity. Their pedagogical and psychological role is incomparable and is manifested in the following aspects:

1. Personal example: Children follow adults and learn their behavior. Qualities such as honesty, fairness, kindness, and responsibility embodied in the leader act as a unique educational school for children.
2. Psychological environment: The leader's courtesy, manners, respect for employees and children create a positive psychological environment. This helps children to feel free and reveal their full potential.
3. Educational influence: Through his pedagogical skills and moral qualities, the leader influences the formation of positive qualities such as correctness, patriotism, hard work in children.
4. Eliminating conflicts: The leader's fairness, patience and high communication culture play an important role in eliminating conflicts that may arise in the team.
5. Encouraging employees: The leader's respect for employees, appreciation of their work, care creates a healthy environment in the team and encourages them to work more efficiently.

Pedagogical consciousness is a set of professional knowledge, value orientations, the teacher's attitude, the nature of the relationship determines his attitude to professional activity; consists of a personal and professional concept. The teacher understands, perceives, evaluates and takes into account the nature of the student and the specific characteristics of pedagogical activity [13].

Pedagogical tactics - adherence to general norms of communication and interaction with children, taking into account their age and individuality, psychological characteristics [14].

In conclusion, the moral qualities of the head of the preschool educational organization have important pedagogical and psychological importance in the formation of children as individuals, in creating a healthy psychological environment in the community, and in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process.

The moral qualities of the leader act as a kind of "invisible teacher" in the educational institution. Their positive influence will be reflected not only today, but also in the future.

In short, the moral qualities of leaders are crucial for the success of an educational institution. They create a healthy atmosphere in the team, inspire students and employees, and contribute to the overall development of the organization.

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